

ANALYSIS OF METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES FOR TECHNICAL ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL AND QUALITY OF GARAGE EQUIPMENT IN PROVIDING TECHNICAL MAINTENANCE OF MOTOR TRANSPORT VEHICLES.

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Annotation

This article investigates the methods for assessing the technical level of garage equipment that was formed simultaneously with the process of forming equipment production as elements of future quality systems of manufacturing enterprises. At the same time, the main task, as a rule, is to evaluate the technical level of its production samples and justify directions for their improvement to increase the level of product quality.

Keywords: Garage, product, product quality, technical preparation, indicator, evaluation, motor vehicle, equipment.

Methods of assessing the technical level of garage equipment were formed simultaneously with the process of forming equipment production as elements of future quality systems of manufacturing enterprises. At the same time, the main task, as a rule, is to evaluate the technical level of its production samples and

justify directions for their improvement to increase the level of product quality. We will consider the main methodological approaches to solving this problem, which are indicated in regulatory documents, and special technical and educational literature.

Evaluation of the technical level of garage equipment according to GOST 15467-79 indicators. Within the framework of the product quality assurance policy at the state level, it is envisaged to evaluate its technical level. GOST 15467-79 "Product quality management" This standard defines product quality indicators and their determination methods. We list the most commonly used part of them in basic practice.

Product quality is a set of characteristics of products that make them suitable for meeting certain needs according to their purpose.

A single indicator of product quality can refer to a unit of product and a unit of products of the same type, representing a simple characteristic.

A complex indicator of product quality represents several simple features or a complex feature of a product consisting of several simple products together.

For example, the coefficient of technical training:

$$K_g = T / (T + T_v) \quad (1)$$

Here T is product failure (reliability indicator); T_v is the average recovery time (repair index).

Product quality indicator used in decision-making:

$$K = \sum_{i=1}^n K_i * q_i \quad (2)$$

Here is the evaluation of one metric in K_i -scores; q_i is the weight of this feature in points.

If the determinant is complex, it is called generalized. If at least one indicator is equal to zero, then the total indicator should be equal to zero, that is, the quality of the product should be considered unsatisfactory.

The integral indicator of product quality is characterized by the ratio of the

total useful effect of using or consuming the product to the total costs for creating and using it:

$$I = \frac{E}{H_y + H_i} \quad (3)$$

Here, E is the overall beneficial effect of using or consuming the product (for example, vehicle mileage in ton-kilometers per service life for repairs); H_y is total costs for creating products (development, production, installation, and other one-time costs). Total costs for using H_i is products (maintenance, repair, and other running costs).

In addition to the integral indicator of product quality, the value of the so-called specific costs per unit of its impact can also be used.

The main value of the product quality indicator is the value taken as the basis for a comparative assessment of its quality.

The relative value of the product quality indicator is the relationship between the values of the quality indicator of the product evaluated at the basic value of this indicator.

The weight coefficient of the product quality indicator is the quantitative characteristic of the importance of the quality indicator among other indicators of its quality.

The technical level of the product is the quality of the product based on the comparison of the values of the relative characteristic indicators, describes the technical excellence of the products evaluated by the main values of the relevant indicators.

Quality is a field of science, its subject is quantitative methods of product quality assessment.

Methods of determining product quality indicators;
 measurement method measurements using technical means;
 recording method-tracking and calculating specific numbers of product or cost events;

the method is calculated based on the use of its parameters from theoretical or empirical relationships of product quality indicators. It is used to forecast product quality;

Expert method - based on the decision made by experts; social method - collecting and analyzing the opinions of its actual or potential consumers.

CONCLUSION

Based on the developed theoretical-methodical and scientific-methodical rules, mathematical models, and technical and technological proposals in the innovative direction, the main scientific problem was solved - the scientific basis for the improvement of the technological equipment for the maintenance of motor vehicles was created.

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